

Research article

Cu and Ga dual sites on Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol

Xuan Lu^{a,b,c}, Xènia Garcia^{a,c,d}, Isabel Serrano^c, Martí Biset-Peiró^b, Jing Yu^{b,e}, Junshan Li^f, Jordi Arbiol^{e,g}, Andreu Cabot^{b,g,*}, Jordi Llorca^{a,c,d,**}

^a Department of Chemical Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, EEBE, Eduard Maristany 10-14, 08019 Barcelona, Spain

^b Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Jardins de Les Dones de Negre 1, 08930 Sant Adrià de Besòs, Spain

^c Institute of Energy Technologies, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, EEBE, Eduard Maristany 10-14, 08019 Barcelona, Spain

^d Barcelona Research Center in Multiscale Science and Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, EEBE, Eduard Maristany 10-14, 08019 Barcelona, Spain

^e Catalan Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology (ICN2), CSIC and BIST, Campus UAB, Bellaterra, 08193 Barcelona, Catalonia Spain

^f Institute for Advanced Study, Chengdu University, 610106 Chengdu, PR China

^g ICREA, Pg. Lluís Companys 23, Barcelona 08010, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Cu-based catalysts are highly attractive for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol due to their efficiency, selectivity, and cost-effectiveness. To further accelerate methanol synthesis, dual-site activation mechanisms are particularly effective. In this direction, solid solutions serve as effective supports, enhancing methanol production through improved hydrogenation, though the exact nature of the active sites in CuGa-based solid solutions remains unclear. In this study, we examine the synergistic interactions between Ga and Cu nanoparticles/clusters deposited on Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ for CO₂-to-methanol hydrogenation. Through *in situ* diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy and temperature-programmed (TPR/TPD), we analyze the nature of the active sites and elucidate the reaction pathway. The results demonstrate that CO₂ adsorption and activation are favored by the appropriate Cu/Ga ratio, while Ga sites, in addition to Cu, play a critical role in promoting H₂ dissociation under methanol synthesis conditions. Furthermore, the oxygen vacancies in the CuGa/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst play a crucial role in stabilizing the key *HCOO intermediate, facilitating its further hydrogenation to methanol via the formate pathway. This synergy between Ga and Cu optimizes both CO₂ activation and hydrogenation steps, emphasizing Ga as an active site alongside Cu and highlighting the catalyst's potential for efficient methanol production from CO₂.

1. Introduction

Converting the greenhouse gas CO₂ into methanol using H₂ derived from renewable sources is a promising economic and sustainable approach for chemical recycling of CO₂, aiming at achieving net zero carbon emissions. Among the various methods for CO₂ transformation into methanol, heterogeneous catalysis stands out due to its superior yield and selectivity [1–7]. To accelerate the industrial application of this process, ongoing research focuses on strategies to reduce catalyst usage while maximizing the active catalytic atoms and maintaining long-term productivity [8–13].

In this context, Cu-based catalysts have attracted particular attention for their superior catalytic activity and selectivity in CO₂ hydrogenation

to methanol, as well as their cost-effectiveness. As an example, Song et al. demonstrated an 8 wt% Cu/ZnAl₂O₄ catalyst that exhibited strong H₂ dissociation capabilities, promoting methanol production through a strong metal-support interaction [14]. Cu species serve as the active site in this reaction, and their properties, such as particle size, dispersion, and the ratio of Cu⁰/Cu⁺, play a critical role in determining catalytic activity [14–24]. Therefore, understanding the relationship between structure and catalytic activity at the atomic level is essential for designing and optimizing high-performance heterogeneous Cu-based catalysts for CO₂-to-methanol conversion. Recent progress in heterogeneous Cu-based catalysts for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol has demonstrated the critical roles of active site design (e.g., Cu⁰/Cu⁺ ratio, oxygen vacancies, and metal-support interactions) in tuning activity and

* Corresponding author at: Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Jardins de Les Dones de Negre 1, 08930 Sant Adrià de Besòs, Spain.

** Corresponding author at: Institute of Energy Technologies and Barcelona Research Center in Multiscale Science and Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Eduard Maristany 16, EEBE, Barcelona 08019, Spain.

E-mail addresses: acabot@irec.cat (A. Cabot), jordi.llorca@upc.edu (J. Llorca).

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selectivity (Table S1).

A dual-site activation mechanism for H_2 has been proposed to accelerate methanol synthesis. In this process, interstitial H atoms in the support material facilitate the formation of formate species from CO_2 , while H atoms dissociated from Cu nanoparticles aid in the hydrogenation of these formate species into methanol. In this direction, Hensen et al. explored the synergistic interaction between Cu and ZnO, CeO_2 , and ZnO- CeO_2 within composite catalysts prepared by flame spray pyrolysis, illustrating the importance of such interactions [18]. Additionally, solid solutions such as $MZrO_x$ ($M = Zn, Ga, Cd, \text{etc.}$) have shown high selectivity and stability at high temperatures, making them excellent supports in Cu-based catalysts for methanol synthesis [9,25–30]. For Ga-based catalysts, Ga-O sites are responsible for H_2 dissociation, supplying Ga-H and -OH species, while CO_2 preferentially adsorbs on unsaturated Zr^{4+} sites [29]. As an example, Xu et al. introduced Cu into a $ZnZrO_x$ solid solution revealing an increase in methanol production by enhancing hydrogenation capacity and promoting H_2 spillover [29]. Despite this progress, the exact nature of the active sites in Cu-based solid solutions remains unclear, partially due to the complex coordination structure of Cu species and the synergistic effect between Cu sites and Ga [31–33]. Karelovic et al. argue that Ga promotion could not be related to electronic changes on the surface copper where Ga works as an active site as Cu for CO_2 hydrogenation to methanol [34]. On the contrary, Park et al. argued that Ga/SBA-15 catalysts hardly produced methanol, where the Cu^+ state varied by the addition of Ga, indicating that Ga is involved as a promotion additive in stabilizing the Cu^+ state [35].

In this work, we aim to gain insight into the synergistic interaction between Cu and Ga in promoting the hydrogenation of CO_2 to methanol. To achieve this, we introduce both Cu and Ga into a $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ solid solution where the weak sintering resistance ability of CeO_2 can be compensated by the incorporation of Zr. In addition, CeO_2 redox capacity also can be enhanced and the ratio of Ce/Zr can result in a different interaction between Cu and Ce, which influences the formation of Cu + species [36,37]. Then we introduce both Cu and Ga into a $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ solid solution, preparing a series of Cu-Ga / $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ samples by varying the Cu/Ga ratio but keeping constant total metal weight. This set of samples is tested for their catalytic performance in CO_2 hydrogenation to methanol. Additionally, we explore the underlying mechanism of CO_2 hydrogenation in relation to the copper content in these samples.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Chemicals

Zirconium(IV) oxynitrate hydrate ($ZrO(NO_3)_2 \cdot xH_2O$, 99.99 %), cerium(III) nitrate hexahydrate ($Ce(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, 99 %), copper(II) nitrate trihydrate ($Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$, 99 %), gallium(III) nitrate hydrate ($Ga(NO_3)_3 \cdot xH_2O$, 99 %), and urea (NH_2CONH_2 , 99 %) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Ethanol was purchased from various sources. All chemicals and reagents were used without any further purification. Deionized (DI) water (18 $M\Omega \cdot cm$) was used in all experiments. A commercial catalyst to be used as a reference for the synthesis of methanol, based on the ternary $CuO-ZnO-Al_2O_3$ (CZA) material, was obtained from Alfa Aesar (45776; mass composition CuO 63.5 %, ZnO 25.1 %, Al_2O_3 10.1 %, MgO 1.3 %).

2.2. Synthesis of $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ solid solution

Zirconium–cerium oxides were synthesized by the urea hydrolysis method [38,39]. Briefly, $ZrO(NO_3)_2 \cdot xH_2O$ and $Ce(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ were dissolved in 100 mL DI water with a total cationic concentration of 0.5 mol L^{-1} . Urea was then dissolved in the aqueous solution with the same ratio as nitrates under vigorous stirring. Then the as-prepared mixed solution was sealed in a hydrothermal reactor at 150 °C for 16 h. The

obtained sample ($Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ -fresh) was centrifuged, washed thoroughly with DI water and ethanol, and dried at 100 °C overnight. Afterward, the pure sample was calcined at 500 °C for 4 h, and it was named $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ -cal.

2.3. Synthesis of Cu-Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$

A series of Cu-Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ catalysts were prepared using the incipient wetness impregnation method (Fig. 1), with varying Cu:Ga weight ratios of 95:5, 75:25, 50:50, 25:75, and 5:95. The total loading of copper and gallium was maintained constant at 3 wt% across all samples. Briefly, $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ and $Ga(NO_3)_3 \cdot xH_2O$ were dissolved in DI water at a 3 M cation concentration. The solution was then added dropwise into 1 g of $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ -fresh. Then, the mixed samples were dried at 60 °C overnight and calcined in air at 500 °C for 4 h with a rate of 5 °C min^{-1} . The resultant samples were labeled xCu-(100-x)Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ where x represents the weight percentage of copper (x = 95, 75, 50, 25, 5).

2.4. Catalyst characterization

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed on a Bruker AXS D8 X-ray diffractometer (Cu-K α radiation, $\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$, 40 kV and 40 mA; Bruker, Germany).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) spectra were obtained with a Zeiss Auriga field emission scanning electron microscopy equipped with an Oxford EDS detector. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM, high-resolution TEM (HRTEM), and high-angle annular dark field scanning TEM (HAADF-STEM) images were acquired in a field emission gun FEI TecnaiF20 microscope operated at 200 kV. Electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) experiments were conducted using a GatanQuantum Filter in the same microscope. Principal component analysis (PCA) from GatanMicroscopy Suite (GMS) 3.4 was employed to eliminate noise from the EELS data.

Inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) was conducted on a 5100 ICP-OES from Agilent Technologies.

The specific surface area was analyzed on a Micromeritics TriStar II 3020 and calculated by the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method.

Hydrogen temperature-programmed reduction (H_2 -TPR) was performed on a Chemstar-TPX instrument equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). Firstly, about 50 mg of catalyst were pretreated at 110 °C (10 °C min^{-1}) under Ar flow (50 mL min^{-1}) for 1 h and then cooled down to 35 °C. The TPR was performed from 35 °C to 850 °C with a constant heating speed of 10 °C min^{-1} under a flow of 10 % H_2 in Ar (50 mL min^{-1}). Pure copper oxide (CuO, 97 %) was used to calibrate the TCD signal.

Temperature-programmed desorption of CO_2 (CO_2 -TPD) was

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of catalyst preparation process.

conducted with an adsorption/desorption system Micromeritics AutoChem HP chemisorption Analyzer. 100 mg of sample was pretreated at 90 °C for 30 min with He. Then, the sample was cooled to 50 °C and reduced *in situ* at 300 °C at a rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ for 1 h under binary gas (10 vol% H₂/Ar). After cooling to temperature and saturating with CO₂ for 1 h, the sample was purged with He for 2 h to remove physically adsorbed CO₂. Subsequently, the sample was heated to 800 °C to record with a rate of 5 °C min⁻¹.

The dispersion (D_{Cu}) and exposed surface area (S_{Cu}) of Cu were determined by N₂O titration on a Micromeritics AutoChem II 2920 instrument. Initially, 100 mg of calcined sample was reduced at 350 °C in a 5 % H₂/Ar mixture (30 mL min⁻¹) for 2h. Subsequently, upon cooling to 60 °C, the sample was exposed to N₂O (30 mL min⁻¹) for 1 h to ensure thorough oxidation of surface metallic copper to Cu₂O. Finally, calibrated hydrogen (5 vol% H₂/Ar) pulse reduction at 350 °C was performed to quantify the quantity of surface Cu₂O species.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was conducted with a SPECS system equipped with an XR-50 X-ray source operating at 150 W and a Phoibos 150 MCD-9 detector. The CuGa/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ precursor was pressed into a thin disc, mounted onto a sample rod, and placed in the pretreatment chamber, where it was pretreated with pure H₂ (20 mL min⁻¹) at 300 °C for 20 min. After pretreatment, the sample was transferred to the analysis chamber. The charging effect was corrected by adjusting the binding energy of the Ce 3d (u''') peak to 917 eV.

In situ DRIFTS was employed to record the spectra of species adsorbed on the catalyst surfaces during CO adsorption and CO₂ hydrogenation. The experiments were conducted using a Bruker VERTEXT 70 spectrometer. The reactor was specially designed to minimize dead volume. Before CO adsorption, all samples were reduced at 300 °C in a 10 % H₂/Ar flow (40 mL min⁻¹, 0.1 MPa) for 60 min, then purged under He flow and cooled to 25 °C to obtain the background spectrum. The gas flow was then adjusted to a 1 % CO/99 % He mixture (40 mL min⁻¹) at the same temperature while collecting spectra for 60 min until the CO adsorption intensity no longer changed. To investigate desorption behavior, the catalyst was purged with He while additional spectra were collected. If the CO adsorption peak persisted after 30 min, further DRIFT spectra were acquired. For CO₂ hydrogenation, all samples were reduced at 300 °C in a 10 % H₂/Ar flow (40 mL min⁻¹, 0.1 MPa) for 60 min, then cooled to 200 °C to obtain the background spectrum. The gas flow was then adjusted to a H₂:CO₂:Ar ratio of 3:1:4 (40 mL min⁻¹) at the same temperature, and spectra were simultaneously collected to monitor changes in the intensity of various surface species.

2.5. Activity tests

The catalytic performance of the catalysts was evaluated in a fixed-bed stainless steel tubular reactor with an inner diameter of 9 mm. Typically, 0.1 g of catalyst was mixed with 0.4 g silicon carbide and reduced at 300 °C for 1 h under atmospheric pressure in a pure hydrogen flow with a ramp rate of 5 °C min⁻¹. The reaction was conducted at 180–300 °C at 3.0 MPa and a gas hourly space velocity (GHSV) of 15,000 mL g⁻¹h⁻¹ with a H₂/CO₂/N₂ molar ratio of 3:1:1. N₂ serves as the internal standard in the experiments. Products were analyzed on-line with an Agilent 490 micro gas chromatograph equipped with thermal conductivity detectors (TCD), employing three columns: Stabilwax, MS 5 Å, and Plot U. All product lines were heated around 130 °C to prevent condensation of products. The carbon balance ($C_{balance}$) was determined for each experiment and confirmed to be above 95 % according to the equation:

$$C_{balance} = \left(\frac{CO_{2,out} + CO_{out} + CH_{4,out} + CH_3OH_{out} + 2DME_{out}}{CO_{2,in}} \right) \times \frac{N_{2,in}}{N_{2,out}} \quad (1)$$

where M_{in} (M: CO₂, N₂, CO, CH₄, CH₃OH and DME) and M_{out} referred to the M concentrations in the inlet and outlet gas.

Conversion (X), selectivity (S), yield (Y), space–time yield (STY) and turnover frequencies of methanol production (TOF_{Cu}) in the catalytic tests were calculated as follows:

$$X(CO_2)(\%) = \left(1 - \frac{CO_{2,out} \times N_{2,in}}{N_{2,out} \times CO_{2,in}} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$S(CH_3OH)(\%) = \left(\frac{CH_3OH_{out}}{CO_{out} + CH_{4,out} + CH_3OH_{out}} \right) \times \frac{N_{2,in}}{N_{2,out}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$Y(CH_3OH) = X(CO_2) \times S(CH_3OH) \quad (4)$$

$$STY_{CH_3OH} = \frac{CO_{2,in} \times Y(CH_3OH)}{22.4 \times m_{CuGa}} \quad (5)$$

$$TOF_{Cu}(s^{-1}) = \frac{CO_{2,in} \times X(CO_2) \times S(CH_3OH)}{22.4 \times D_{Cu} \times m_{Cu}} \quad (6)$$

where m_{CuGa} is the mass of Cu and Ga of the catalyst, m_{Cu} is the mass of Cu of the catalyst, D_{Cu} is the copper dispersion of the catalyst and where $N_{2,in}$ and $N_{2,out}$ referred to the N₂ concentrations in the inlet and outlet gas.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalytic performance

Understanding the relationship between reaction temperature, copper content, and catalyst performance is essential in optimizing CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol. To assess this, experiments were conducted at various temperatures (180, 210, 240, 270, and 300 °C). CO was the only detected byproduct of the reaction, originating from the reverse water–gas shift reaction (rWGS) (Fig. S1) [40]. For all tested Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts, as well as the reference CZA catalyst, CO₂ conversion showed a moderate increase between 180 to 270 °C, followed by a more significant rise above 270 °C (Fig. 2a). As the temperature increased, a gradual decrease in methanol selectivity from 100 to 40 % was obtained for all catalysts except 5Cu-95 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ (Fig. 2b), indicating a thermodynamic shift toward CO production via rWGS. Except for this catalyst, 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ maintained significantly higher methanol selectivities, particularly when compared with commercial CZA, suggesting that the Ga-promoted Cu/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ interface suppresses rWGS by stabilizing formate (HCOO) and methoxy (OCH₃) intermediates, as evidenced by *in situ* DRIFTS (Fig. 10). Consistently, the Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts demonstrated a superior STY of methanol compared to the commercial CZA catalyst, particularly when normalized to the amount of copper and gallium (Fig. 2c). These catalysts showed superior metal activity with increasing temperature compared with commercial catalyst CZA. Even though the 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst showed a slightly lower STY of methanol compared to the 50Cu-50 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst (Fig. S2-6), it remained competitive due to its large MeOH selectivity at higher temperature. The 5Cu-95 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst exhibited anomalous selectivity (near 100 % at all temperatures), likely due to its low Cu loading, which limits CO-producing sites. However, its low STY (Fig. 2c) reflects insufficient active sites for practical application. Additionally, 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst exhibited an apparent activation energy (E_a) for methanol synthesis of 25.8 kJ mol⁻¹, as calculated from the Arrhenius equation (Fig. 2d), which is significantly lower than that of CZA (55.0 kJ mol⁻¹) and other copper-loaded catalysts. This difference arises from the synergistic effects of Ga doping and the Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ support: (1) Ga enhances H₂ dissociation and spillover to Cu sites, accelerating hydrogenation steps; (2) Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ redox pairs facilitate CO₂ activation via oxygen vacancy-mediated pathways.

To investigate the intrinsic activity of surface copper on these catalysts, the turnover frequency of copper (TOF_{Cu}), defined as the number of methanol molecules produced per surface copper atom per second

Fig. 2. Catalytic performance of Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts and commercial CuO-ZnO-Al₂O₃ (CZA) catalyst in the CO₂ hydrogenation reaction to methanol. (a) CO₂ conversion, (b) methanol (MeOH) selectivity, (c) methanol space-time yield, and (d) Arrhenius plot. Reaction conditions: GHSV = 15,000 mL g⁻¹ h⁻¹, H₂:CO₂:N₂ = 3:1:1, 3.0 MPa.

(s⁻¹), was calculated and is presented in Fig. S7. The TOF_{Cu} values of all CuGa-based catalysts were compared at 270 °C, revealing that 75Cu-25 Ga exhibited the highest TOF value (1.4 s⁻¹), indicating an optimal balance between copper dispersion and active site availability. In

contrast, 5Cu-95 Ga and 25Cu-75 Ga, despite exhibiting the highest dispersion, showed lower TOF values, likely due to excessive gallium hindering the effectiveness of Cu active sites. Higher copper loading (95Cu-5 Ga) resulted in reduced catalytic activity, suggesting that

Fig. 3. Stability test of the 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst. The red and green data points show the methanol selectivity and CO₂ conversion rate, respectively. Blue data show the STY of methanol. Black data show carbon balance over time. Reaction conditions: GHSV = 15,000 mL g⁻¹ h⁻¹, T = 270 °C, H₂: CO₂: N₂ = 3:1:1, 3.0 MPa. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

excessive Cu may lead to agglomeration, thereby limiting active site accessibility. The commercial CZA catalyst exhibited the lowest TOF value (0.88 s^{-1}), further emphasizing the superior efficiency of 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts for methanol synthesis. These findings highlight the importance of optimizing the copper-to-gallium ratio in Cu-Ga-based catalysts to enhance catalytic performance in methanol production.

The long-term stability test showed the 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst to exhibit excellent durability, with no noticeable decline in both selectivity and activity throughout 110 h at 270 °C and 3 Mpa. The catalyst maintained a consistent CO₂ conversion rate of around 4 % and a methanol selectivity of ca. 98 % throughout the test (Fig. 3). These results suggest that optimized Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts can provide superior selectivity for high-temperature methanol synthesis via CO₂ hydrogenation when compared to standard CZA catalysts.

3.2. Catalyst characterization

The physicochemical properties of the Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts and the reference CZA are summarized in Table 1. The surface area of Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ ranges from 53.4 m² g⁻¹ to 74.2 m² g⁻¹, well above that of CZA (28.7 m² g⁻¹). As the copper content increases in Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, the Cu dispersion (D_{Cu}) gradually decreases, while the Cu metal surface area (S_{Cu}) increases. For 5Cu-95 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ and 25Cu-75 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, a 100 % Cu dispersion, measured by N₂O titration, suggests the presence of Cu single atoms. In contrast, in 50Cu-50 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂a, 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, and 95Cu-5 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, metal clusters and nanoparticles are likely formed. While higher copper dispersion generally provides more active sites, the dissociation of H₂ is more efficiently facilitated by the presence of adjacent metal centers. This explains the catalytic performance trend observed in Fig. 2, highlighting that both the copper content and copper dispersion are crucial factors influencing the catalytic behaviour of these materials.

To further investigate the morphology and nanostructure of the catalysts, SEM and TEM analyses were conducted. As shown in the SEM images (Fig. S8), the catalysts exhibit irregularly shaped blocks with sizes ranging from 20 to 40 nm. HRTEM micrographs of the 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst (Fig. 4a) reveal the presence of Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ (cyan squared area in Fig. 4a) and also some dispersed ZrO₂ (red squared area in Fig. 4a) nanoparticles. In the case of the Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ nanoparticle shown in the red and orange squared area, we found the typical 0.32 nm and 0.27 nm lattice spacings of corresponding to the (11-1) and (200) lattice planes as visualized along the [011] zone axis, respectively. These lattice parameters perfectly fit the cubic Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ support phase. The FFT obtained on the nanoparticle shown in the red and orange squared area, shows spots with spacings corresponding to the (1-1-1), (11-1), and (020) lattice planes as visualized along the [101] zone axis of the ZrO₂ cubic phase, respectively. Notably, no obvious Cu and Ga large particles were observed throughout the microscopy

analysis, likely due to their low concentrations. HRTEM images and FFT analysis of localized areas revealed lattice spacings of 0.184 nm and 0.196 nm, corresponding to the interplanar distances of the (111) plane of Cu and the (112) plane of Ga, respectively, which might form Cu and Ga small clusters. Further analysis using EELS mappings of the 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst demonstrates a homogeneous distribution of Cu and Ga across the material (Fig. 4b and Fig. S9).

The XRD patterns of the CuGa/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts with varying Cu/(Ga + Cu) weight ratios display well-resolved diffraction peaks at 28.6°, 33.1°, 47.6° and 56.3°, corresponding to the (111), (200), (220) and (311) lattice planes, respectively, of the cubic Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ phase (Figs. 4c and S10). Additionally, XRD peaks at 24.3°, 31.5°, and 49.8° belong to the monoclinic ZrO₂ phase. Notably, no discernible peaks corresponding to gallium phases, such as Ga₂O₃, are detected, which may be due to the low gallium loading, atomic-level Ga distributions, or the presence of amorphous Ga-based phases. In contrast, while no crystalline Cu phases are observed in samples with a relative copper content below 50 %, distinct CuO peaks emerge when the copper content reaches 50 % (Fig. 4c right). Upon reduction of the 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst in 10 % H₂/Ar at 300 °C, metallic copper peaks become evident (Fig. 4d). Furthermore, the XRD pattern of the spent catalyst was analyzed to investigate structural changes after the CO₂ hydrogenation reaction. The results indicate that both the support and active metal remained stable throughout the reaction.

To understand how the Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts work for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol, we investigate the adsorption/activation of CO₂ on them using CO₂-TPD. The CO₂ adsorption regions are divided into two main sections (Fig. 5a). The front peak (α , 50–200 °C) is ascribed to weak CO₂ adsorption sites [14,32,41,42]. These weak basic sites are assigned to the surface hydroxyl groups of the support, leading to the formation of thermally unstable bicarbonate species. As shown in Table S2, the number of basic sites on the Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ support (Fig. S10) is 0.19 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, while the introduction of Ga and Cu over 5Cu-95 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ increases the basic sites to 0.24 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, suggesting a correlation with Cu and/or Ga content. Despite the decrease in Ga content, the number of basic sites on Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts increases, indicating that weak basic strength is independent of Ga content (Table S2). The moderately basic sites (β , 200–350 °C) are attributed to CO₂ adsorbed onto metal-oxygen pairs. As copper content increases and Ga decreases, there is a marked increase in weak basic sites and a slight increase in moderately basic sites. This suggests that surface Cu species in nanoscale or cluster form likely contribute to intermediate CO₂ adsorption and enhance the metal-support interaction (MSI) between Cu and Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ which is attributed to the reduction of the dispersed Cu species. In contrast to Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts, CZA catalysts exhibit not only weak and moderately basic sites (Fig. S11a), but also strong basic sites (350–500 °C). Previous studies have reported that these strong adsorption sites, resulting from significant bulk copper incorporation into the support, negatively affect methanol selectivity in CO₂ hydrogenation.

Table 1
Physicochemical properties of Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts.

Catalyst	Cu loading ^a (wt %)	Ga loading ^a (wt %)	D _{Cu} ^b (%)	S _{Cu} ^c (m ² g ⁻¹)	S _{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	Pore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹)
5Cu-95 Ga/Ce _{0.9} Zr _{0.1} O ₂	0.2	3.6	100	1.3	66.0	0.12
25Cu-75 Ga/Ce _{0.9} Zr _{0.1} O ₂	0.8	2.5	100	5.2	53.4	0.11
50Cu-50 Ga/Ce _{0.9} Zr _{0.1} O ₂	1.6	1.3	87.6	9.0	58.6	0.11
75Cu-25 Ga/Ce _{0.9} Zr _{0.1} O ₂	2.3	0.7	74.6	10.5	74.2	0.10
95Cu-5 Ga/Ce _{0.9} Zr _{0.1} O ₂	2.9	0.3	65.8	12.3	62.6	0.10
CZA	50.7	0	19.7	64.4	28.7	0.10
Ce _{0.9} Zr _{0.1} O ₂ -fresh	–	–	–	–	17.8	0.04
Ce _{0.9} Zr _{0.1} O ₂ -cal	–	–	–	–	91.7	0.23

^a Measured by ICP-OES/MS.

^b Cu dispersion was determined by N₂O titration.

^c Cu metal surface area is based on an atomic surface density of 1.46×10^{19} Cu atoms m⁻².

Fig. 4. (a) HRTEM micrographs of 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ with selected magnified details corresponding to the red, blue and yellow squared areas, together with their respective FFT patterns. (b) HAADF-STEM image and EELS maps for 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂. XRD patterns of (c) Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts and (d) 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ before reaction (fresh), after reduction in 10 % H₂/Ar (reduced) and after long-time stability test (reacted). Reaction condition: GHSV = 15,000 mL g⁻¹h⁻¹, T = 270 °C, H₂:CO₂:N₂ = 3:1:1, 3.0 MPa. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

H₂-TPR analysis was conducted to examine the reducibility of the different samples in an H₂ environment (Fig. 5b). A significant hydrogen consumption signal is observed in the high-temperature range (300–450 °C) for the 5Cu-95 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts. This is attributed

to the reduction of Ga oxide (Fig. S13). No peak at lower temperatures (100–300 °C) is observed, due to the low content and high dispersion of copper within the 5Cu-95 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ oxide, making it difficult to reduce [17,43,44]. In contrast, samples with higher copper content,

Fig. 5. (a) CO₂-TPD on Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts. (b) H₂-TPR profiles of Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts.

particularly 50Cu-50 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ and 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, exhibit hydrogen consumption at lower temperatures, which correlates with the presence of more accessible Cu species and their superior catalytic performance. In samples with the higher copper content, 50Cu-50 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, and 95Cu-5 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, a minor H₂ consumption peak (α) below 200°C is attributed to the reduction of the surface of CuO particles. The reduction peak β , appearing in the 200–300 °C range, corresponds to the reduction of bulk CuO. This observation aligns with that of the CZA catalyst, which exhibits a single reduction peak at 247°C (Fig. S9b). Interestingly, the β peak for 25Cu-75 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ appears larger than that of 50 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ and 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, despite its lower Cu content (0.8 wt% compared to 1.6 wt% and 2.3 wt%, respectively). This seemingly counterintuitive result can be explained by considering the role of gallium. The 25CuGa sample contains significantly more Ga (2.5 wt%) than 50 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ (1.3 wt%) and 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ (0.7 wt %), which promotes the dispersion of Cu species and enhances Cu-Ga interactions. These effects lead to the formation of highly dispersed Cu-Ga-O species with greater reducibility, resulting in a more intense β peak. In contrast, higher Cu loading in 50 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ and 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ promotes agglomeration into larger CuO particles with weaker support interaction and lower reducibility, thereby diminishing their contribution to the β peak. Meanwhile, the reduction peaks at 362 and 496 °C over Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ can be assigned to the coordinatively unsaturated Zr⁴⁺ species and the surface Ce⁴⁺ to Ce³⁺, respectively,

whereas the temperatures higher than 700 °C belong to the reduction of bulk Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ (Fig. S13). These results suggest that an optimal Cu/Ga ratio slightly decreases the reduction temperature and modifies the support surface to enhance CO₂ adsorption and activation. The interplay between Cu and Ga content plays a crucial role in tuning the reducibility, dispersion, and consequently, the catalytic behavior of the Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ system.

The Raman spectra of the Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts, presented in Fig. 6a, reveal distinct peaks at 258, 460, 610, and 1173 cm⁻¹ assigned to the Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ second-order transverse acoustic mode (2TA), the lattice (F_{2g}), defect-induced mode (D), and second-order longitudinal optical mode (2LO), respectively [45–48]. As the copper content increases, the intensity of the 2TA and F_{2g} bands weakens, suggesting a decrease in the symmetry of the Ce-O bonds due to the interaction between copper and the Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ support (Fig. S14) [46]. Additionally, a band at 1042 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the ν_1 vibration mode of carbonate anions, while the band at 830 cm⁻¹ is assigned to peroxo species (O₂²⁻) adsorbed on defect sites of ceria. Moreover, a characteristic band at 336 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the copper oxide phase, becomes more prominent with increasing copper content.

After reducing the catalysts in 10 % H₂/Ar at 300 °C, the carbonate, peroxo and copper oxide bands disappeared (Fig. 6b). The ratio of the intensities for the D band and F_{2g} band were estimated to evaluate oxygen vacancy (O_v) concentrations on the Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts before and after reduction (Fig. S15). As the Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂

Fig. 6. Raman spectra of (a) the calcined Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts and (b) the reduced Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂.

catalysts underwent further reduction, a significant increase in the I_D/I_{F2g} ratio was observed, indicating the formation of O_v attributed to the reduction of Ce^{4+} to Ce^{3+} on the $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ surface. With the incorporation of copper, the I_D/I_{F2g} ratio increased, indicating copper's preference to integrate into the surface lattice of the $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ support, leading to a higher defect concentration. Additionally, Cu may enhance O_v formation by promoting the reduction of Ce^{4+} to Ce^{3+} through hydrogen spillover and the weakening of Ce-O bonds [47].

The chemical states of Ce 3d and O 1s on the surface of reduced catalysts were examined using *in situ* XPS (Fig. 7a, b). The Ce 3d XPS spectra consist of two sets of spin-orbital multiplets (Fig. 7a). The peaks labeled v^0 (880.5 eV), v (882.5 eV), v' (884.4 eV), v'' (888.9 eV) and v''' (898.4 eV) are attributed to Ce $3d_{5/2}$, while those labeled u^0 (899.1 eV), u (901.1 eV), u' (903.0 eV), u'' (907.5 eV) and u''' (917 eV) belong to Ce $3d_{3/2}$. The peaks v^0 , v' , u^0 and u' are contributed to Ce^{3+} while the remaining six peaks could be assigned to Ce^{4+} species. The surface concentration of Ce^{3+} was calculated via the ratio of $Ce^{3+}/(Ce^{3+}+Ce^{4+})$, which is related to the surface oxygen vacancies caused by the reduction of Ce^{4+} . Table S3 presents the concentration of Ce^{3+} species in different catalysts. Among them, 25Cu-75 Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ has the highest Ce^{3+} ratio (0.41), i.e. the highest density of surface oxygen vacancies, followed by 75Cu-25 Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ (0.36) and 95Cu-95 Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ (0.31).

The O 1s XPS spectra reveal three peaks (Fig. 7b). The main peak (O_α) at 529.8 eV is assigned to lattice oxygen, the peak (O_β) at 531.5 eV corresponds to surface oxygen species strongly bound to surface oxygen vacancies, and the peak (O_γ) at 532.5 eV is associated with weakly bound surface oxygen species. The ratio of $O_\beta/(O_\alpha + O_\beta + O_\gamma)$ can be indicative of the density of surface oxygen vacancies.⁴⁶ As shown in

Table S3, the concentration of O_β was 0.31 on the 25Cu-75 Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$, slightly decreasing to 0.29 on the 75Cu-25 Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$, and then to 0.23 on the 95Cu-5 Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ sample. The slight decrease might be caused by the higher copper loading limiting the direct contact of copper with oxygen vacancy (O_v) sites on the ceria surface. This stabilization of copper on the ceria surface involves charge transfer between Cu^0 and neighboring Ce^{4+} under reductive conditions, where Ce^{4+} is partially reduced to Ce^{3+} , while Cu^0 is oxidized to Cu^+ . To further confirm the presence of oxygen vacancies in the Cu-Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ catalysts, electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy was conducted, and the results are presented in Fig. S16. All EPR signals are symmetric with g-values of 2.003, indicating the presence of unpaired electrons associated with oxygen vacancies. The signal intensities reflect the relative densities of oxygen vacancies in the following order: 95Cu-5 Ga > 75Cu-25 Ga > 50Cu-50 Ga > 25Cu-75 Ga > 5Cu-95 Ga. This trend is consistent with the results obtained from XPS results and the Raman D/F_{2g} ratios.

To gain additional insight into the relationship between copper content and catalytic performance, the Cu 2p XPS and Cu LM2 Auger spectra were analyzed before and after a long-time stability test (Figs. 7c, S17c and S18). The binding energy of Cu $2p_{3/2}$ peak is approximately 932.8 eV, with Auger signals at 918.2 eV, indicating the presence of Cu^0 in the reduced samples. Notably, a new feature appeared at 910 eV in the reduced samples but was absent in the reacted catalyst (Fig. S18). Yano et al. argued that this feature could arise from the main Auger signal of copper cations within a specific chemical environment, where a highly localized hole in the 3d orbitals reduces the kinetic energy of emitted electrons relative to Cu^+ . However, no obvious signal attributed to Cu^+ was detected in Cu LM2 spectra, suggesting that small

Fig. 7. (a) Ce 3d, (b) O 1s, (c) Cu 2p, and (d) Ga 2p XPS spectra of reduced catalysts. The Cu-Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ precursor was reduced with pure H_2 (20 mL min^{-1}) at 300 °C for 20 min in a pretreatment chamber and the reduced Cu-Ga/ $Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O_2$ catalysts were directly transferred into the analysis chamber.

Cu⁰ clusters contact oxygen vacancy sites^{47,48}, consistent with the results of copper dispersion (Table 1) and XRD (Fig. 4). The Cu 2p spectra confirmed the absence of Cu²⁺ (Cu 2p_{1/2}: ~963 eV), although a weak Cu⁺ satellite peak was observed on 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ after the reaction (Fig. S14c). The Cu 2p spectra confirmed the absence of Cu²⁺ (Cu 2p_{1/2}: ~963 eV), although a weak Cu⁺ satellite peak was observed on 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ after the reaction (Fig. S14c). This result is in line with the Cu LM2 Auger spectra, where a peak at 915.1 eV, attributed to Cu⁺, was detected (Fig. S18b). This Cu⁺ is considered an active site for methanol synthesis, enhancing methanol selectivity in CO₂ hydrogenation.

The high-resolution Ga 2p spectra are shown in Fig. 8d. The two peaks at 1145.3 and 1118.4 eV observed for the as-prepared 25Cu-75 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ correspond to Ga 2p_{1/2} and Ga 2p_{3/2} of gallium oxide, respectively. A negative shift of the Ga 2p_{3/2} peak to 1120.3 eV, assigned to the Ga³⁺ state in the reduced 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, suggests the presence of Ga-OH species. This change modifies the methanol adsorption properties of the catalysts, resulting in higher selectivity for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol.

The comparison of fresh and reacted catalysts after long-term stability tests (Fig. 7 and S17), overall indicate that the elemental valence states and chemical composition of the 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst were well preserved, consistent with the good long-term catalytic performance (Fig. 3). This suggests that the Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst is stable for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol production.

3.3. In situ DRIFTS

In situ CO-DRIFTS spectra reveal that under CO flow (Fig. S25), 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ exhibits the strongest CO adsorption signal at approximately 2108 cm⁻¹. This peak corresponds to linearly adsorbed CO on Cu⁺ sites, indicating a high dispersion of accessible Cu⁺ species-likely in the form of small Cu clusters-compared to 25Cu-75 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ and 95Cu-5 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂. After purging with helium, the peak shifts slightly to 2106 cm⁻¹ and decreases in intensity, suggesting reversible CO adsorption and moderate CO-Cu⁺ interactions. The weaker signal observed for 95CuGa implies potential Cu agglomeration, which reduces the number of active surface sites. Conversely, 25Cu-75 Ga may contain insufficient Cu to provide adequate active sites. These findings suggest that 75Cu-25 Ga achieves an optimal balance between Cu and Ga, enhancing the availability of Cu⁺ sites. In CO₂ hydrogenation, such Cu clusters are crucial, as they facilitate CO₂ activation and subsequent hydrogenation, particularly through the formation of key formate intermediates. The incorporation of Ga plays a vital role in stabilizing small, dispersed Cu⁺ sites by preventing sintering and suppressing bulk Cu formation. Additionally, Ga can donate electrons, modifying the Cu electronic environment to strengthen CO binding and promote intermediate formation. Thus, the synergistic interaction between Cu clusters and Ga results in an active and selective surface for

CO₂ hydrogenation, with 75Cu-25 Ga demonstrating superior catalytic performance.

To investigate whether both Cu and Ga promote H₂ activation and dissociation, we performed H₂-DRIFTS experiments on 5Cu-95 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, and 95Cu-5 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ (Figs. S19–S21). To minimize the influence of adsorbed H* species from the pretreatment, we subjected the samples to vacuum conditions prior to H₂-DRIFTS. Upon H₂ exposure, a peak at 2115 cm⁻¹, attributed to Ga-H, was observed, while no Cu-H peaks were detected (Fig. S19). Simultaneously, numerous hydroxyl group peaks (3400–3100 cm⁻¹) appeared. Switching the feed gas from H₂ + He to He resulted in the disappearance of the Ga-H peak. As the copper content increased, the Cu-H peaks (2050–1900 cm⁻¹) became more prominent, whereas the Ga-H peak diminished. These findings indicate that Ga, like Cu, serves as active sites for H₂ activation and dissociation at 275 °C. Combined with H₂-TPR analysis, the results suggest that an optimal Cu/Ga ratio enhances H₂ adsorption and activation. This enhancement is attributed to the synergistic effect of H₂ dissociation at Ga sites interacting with oxygen vacancies, which play a crucial role in the catalytic process.

To study the evolution of the intermediate species, *in situ* DRIFTS spectra were obtained over 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ during CO₂ adsorption (Fig. 8). After exposure to CO₂, bicarbonate species (around 3620, 1423, and 1216 cm⁻¹) and monodentate carbonate (1338 and 1040 cm⁻¹) are formed. Moreover, the peaks at 1609, 1550, and 1278 cm⁻¹ are assigned to bidentate carbonate [16,26]. By changing the feed gas into a mixture of CO₂ + H₂, the intensities of the peaks assigned to bicarbonate gradually decreased, and new peaks at 2950, 1583, and 1373 cm⁻¹ appeared. The peak located at 1583 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the O-C-O stretching vibration of formate species while that at 1373 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the C-H bending vibration (donated as *HCOO). The corresponding C-H stretching vibration of the formate species is clearly seen at 2846 cm⁻¹. The bands at 1000–1200 cm⁻¹ are assigned to the stretching vibration of the C-O bond in the methoxy group (*H₃CO), while the feature at 2950 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the asymmetric vibration of the C-H bond of the methoxy species.

In situ DRIFT spectra were further recorded at increasing temperatures on different catalysts (Figs. 9 and S22 and 23). At lower temperatures, almost no detectable signals for formate and methoxy species were observed. However, upon increasing the temperature to 240 °C, the signals for formate species significantly intensified, along with those for methoxy species. Upon heating to 300 °C, two CO adsorption bands appeared at 2173 cm⁻¹ and 2110 cm⁻¹, assigned to CO adsorbed on unsaturated Ce⁴⁺ cations and Cu⁺ species [49], respectively, while the intensities of the signals attributed to formate and methyl groups plateaued (Fig. S24). For the CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol, there are two proposed mechanism pathways: the formate [50] and the RWGS + CO-hydrogenation routes [51]. For 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, CO* bands (2100–2200 cm⁻¹) were absent from 200 to 270 °C, suggesting that the formate pathway dominates under these conditions. Only at 300 °C do

Fig. 8. *In situ* DRIFTS spectra of CO₂ adsorption and hydrogenation process over reduced 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst. Reduction conditions: 300 °C for 1 h in 10 % H₂/Ar mix flow (40 mL min⁻¹). Reaction conditions: CO₂/H₂/Ar = 5/15/20 (40 mL min⁻¹), 275 °C, 0.1 MPa.

Fig. 9. *In situ* DRIFTS spectra of 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ during the CO₂ + H₂ reaction at different temperatures, 210 °C (blue), 240 °C (olive), 270 °C (orange) and 300 °C (magenta). Reduction conditions: 300 °C for 1 h in 10 % H₂/He mix flow (40 mL min⁻¹). Reaction conditions: CO₂/H₂/He = 5/15/20 (40 mL min⁻¹). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the bands at 2173 and 2110 cm⁻¹ become visible, indicating that CO-related intermediates form appreciably only at elevated temperatures, likely due to the onset of RWGS. This correlates well with the observed high methanol selectivity (>99 %) maintained up to 270 °C, as the catalytic surface favors the stabilization of formate and methoxy intermediates over CO. Although both 25Cu-75 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ and 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ exhibit CO adsorption bands at 300 °C, their catalytic behaviors diverge significantly. 25Cu-75 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ shows an early drop in methanol selectivity starting from 210 °C, while 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ remains highly selective up to 270 °C. This discrepancy suggests that, despite similar Cu⁺ and Ce⁴⁺-CO interactions at higher temperature, the hydrogen activation capability differs due to the Ga environment. 25Cu-75 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, with higher Ga loading (2.5 wt%) but lower Cu content (0.8 wt% less than 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂), may possess Ga species that are not optimally situated to form reactive Ga-H intermediates or may form less stable ones. In contrast, 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ (0.7 wt% Ga) appears to maintain a favorable Cu-Ga interaction, where Ga acts as an active site for H₂ dissociation, complementing Cu⁺ sites for CO₂ activation. This balance leads to more efficient hydrogenation via the formate route and suppresses CO formation until higher temperatures. In comparison, 95Cu-5 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ exhibits only a broad CO band at 2121 cm⁻¹, consistent with CO adsorbed on metallic Cu⁰. The lack of Ga-H-driven hydrogenation and the diminished Cu⁺ population result in the predominance of the RWGS pathway, reflected in its significantly lower methanol selectivity. These findings underscore that Ga is not merely a structural promoter but an active site for H₂ dissociation, likely forming Ga-H species that are crucial for methanol synthesis via the formate pathway. The synergistic balance between Ga-H formation, Cu⁺-mediated CO₂ activation, and Ce⁴⁺ oxygen storage is key to achieving high methanol selectivity and suppressing CO formation.

To further investigate the reaction mechanism and the influence of Cu/Ga composition in CO₂ hydrogenation, density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed on representative catalysts: 25Cu-75 Ga, 75Cu-25 Ga, and 95Cu-5 Ga (Fig. 10). The calculated free energies of key intermediates involved in the CO₂ hydrogenation process (*CO₂, *COOH, *HCOO, and *CO) are summarized in Table S4. On the Cu-rich 95Cu-5 Ga surface, the low *CO₂ adsorption energy ($\Delta G = +0.15$ eV) and exergonic *COOH formation ($\Delta G = +0.57$ eV) drive rapid CO production via the RWGS reaction, further intensified by strong *CO binding ($\Delta G = -0.16$ eV), which poisons active sites. In contrast, the Ga-balanced 75Cu-25 Ga surface achieves optimal performance by stabilizing the formate pathway (*HCOO, $\Delta G = -0.57$ eV), while maintaining moderate *CO₂ activation ($\Delta G = +0.28$ eV) and weak *CO adsorption ($\Delta G = -0.07$ eV), resulting in 100 % methanol selectivity. The Ga-rich 25Cu-75 Ga surface, on the other hand, suffers from inefficient CO₂ activation ($\Delta G = +0.55$ eV) due to excessive Ga³⁺ site blocking, although its weak *CO binding ($\Delta G = -0.11$ eV) prevents

Fig. 10. Calculated energy diagram for CO₂ hydrogenation to *CO₂, *COOH, *HCOO and *CO species on 25Cu-75 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ and 95Cu-5 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts.

RWGS from dominating. This study demonstrates that Ga³⁺ modulates the electronic structure of Cu sites to steer selectivity: isolated Cu⁺-Ga³⁺ pairs in 75Cu-25 Ga favor *HCOO hydrogenation, while contiguous Cu⁰ sites in 95Cu-5 Ga promote *CO desorption, and Ga overcrowding in 25Cu-75 Ga kinetically limits CO₂ activation. According to these findings, a proposed reaction pathway for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol over 25Cu-75 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ and 95Cu-5 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst is summarized in Fig. 11.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrated the formation of highly efficient catalytic active sites between copper and gallium, significantly enhancing the catalytic activity for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol. Notably, the 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst exhibited an exceptional methanol formation rate of 2.5×10^3 mg_{MeOH} g_{Cu}⁻¹ h⁻¹ at 270 °C and 3.0 MPa, achieving 100 % methanol selectivity. The outstanding catalytic performance of these catalysts is attributed to the synergistic interaction between copper and gallium, as evidenced by spectroscopic analyses. The appropriate Cu/Ga ratio to modify the support surface enhances CO₂ adsorption and activation, facilitated by the compensatory production of H₂ dissociation at Ga sites that directly interact with oxygen vacancies, which play a critical role in the catalytic process. DRIFTS results further revealed that CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol over these Cu-Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalysts proceed via the formate pathway. Overall, this study provides valuable insights into the synergistic effects of Cu-Ga-based catalysts in CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol.

Fig. 11. Proposed reaction mechanism for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol over (a) 75Cu-25 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂, (b) 25Cu-75 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ and (c) 95Cu-5 Ga/Ce_{0.9}Zr_{0.1}O₂ catalyst.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Xuan Lu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Xènia Garcia:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Isabel Serrano:** Resources, Investigation, Data curation. **Martí Biset-Peiró:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation. **Jing Yu:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Junshan Li:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Jordi Arbiol:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Andreu Cabot:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jordi Llorca:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcat.2025.116295>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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